

Sum Analysis for Integrals.

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Abstract

The paper covers several definitions that are made to be used for sum analysis; their purpose has been kept abstract for flexibility reasons.

1 DEFINITIONS

We assume $x \in \mathbb{R}$, $a, b \in \mathbb{N}$, $b > a > 0$ for:

1.1 DEFINITION OF THE S-INTEGRAL:

$$I_1(a, b, u, n) := \int_a^b \Phi(t, u, n) dt \quad (1)$$

1.2 DEFINITION OF THE Φ -FUNCTION:

$$\Phi(t, u, n) = \sum_{k=1}^n \left(\frac{dt}{du} \cdot u \right), \quad t > 0, \quad n > k \quad (2)$$

2 INTRODUCTION

3 LEMMAS

4 CONCLUSION

5 REFERENCES